

Assessment of Attitude towards Acquisition of Chemistry Content Knowledge among Students in Federal College of Education Zaria, Kaduna State

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Abstract

This study was conducted to assess the attitude on acquisition of chemistry content knowledge among students in Federal College of Education Zaria, Kaduna State. Descriptive survey design was adopted in this study. The population of the study consists of all chemistry students in Federal College of Education Zaria. Sample size of 150 (50 Male and 100 Female) students were selected from Chemistry Department during the 2023/2024 academic session using simple random sampling technique. The study adapted Martha Tapia Attitude towards Chemistry questionnaires. The data collected were tested and analyzed using SPSS V 18. Descriptive frequencies, independent t-test and one-way ANOVA analysis at a confidence level of 0.05 were carried out. The study highlighted that the overall Nigeria Certificate in Education Chemistry students' attitudes toward Chemistry were moderate however, there was no statistically significant differences based on their gender or level of study. The study therefore concluded that the decline in positive attitude of students towards chemistry as their level of studies increases could be attributed to the high demand that learning required at higher levels. It is recommended that Chemistry lecturers should made Chemistry vivid and easy to understand in order to motivate students' intellectual curiosity, which will in turn leads to learning enhancement regardless of their career of choices.

Keywords: Chemistry content knowledge, attitude, gender, level of study

Introduction

Students' academic success has been the focus of researches in science education. As such, effects of several innovative strategies such as inquiry and discovery learning, advance organizers, activity-based learning, and so on, were examined on academic achievement in science subjects. Perhaps, this is because inappropriate teaching methodologies was considered as a dominant factor adduced to students' under-achievement in sciences (Ngeme, 2016; Odhiambo, 2016). However, academic success may be directly or indirectly linked to many other affective factors which among others include attitude, self-efficacy, motivation, and anxiety (Wan & Ma, 2013). Attitudes, like achievement are crucial outcomes of science education as such, every teacher is charged with the responsibility of promoting students' positive attitude towards learning (Yunus & Ali, 2018). The concept of attitude has been widely debated over the years and one of the conclusions drawn was that attitude represents a multidimensional construct the cognitive, affective, and behavioral (Musengimana et al., 2018). Hence, attitude is a concept of belief which may be positive or negative and indicate like or dislike towards an item. Essentially attitude are considered nor to be resistant reform, that is, will students' attitude change through direct and indirect learning, observations. Experiences, and learning environment (Heng & Karpudewan, 2014).

Undoubtedly, gender as an important factor interacting with attitude towards science cannot be overlooked, especially with increasing emphasis on how to boost man power for technological development as well as increasing the population or females

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in the field of science and technology. The issue of gender differences in researches in science education is inconclusive. For instance, the studies of Heug and Karpudewau (2014), Ratarnun and Osman (2018) reported significant gender difference in students' attitude towards chemistry while Wahyudiati et al, (2020); Majere et al. (2012) no significant gender difference in student's attitude towards chemistry. It is therefore, a focus in this study to contribute to literature by exploring influence of gender on students' attitudes towards Chemistry.

Attitude is one of the popular hypothetical construct used to explain phenomena of ones' interest, the way people think, how they feel and how things are being carried out (Heng & Karpudewan, 2014). Hence, attitude could be a good predictor of students' choice of subject. Especially, in the context of science education where students favour certain science subjects. Essentially, while attitude have powerful effect on behavior, this same influence can also create attitudinal change. That is, attitude are not set in stone and can be reinforced. In view of this, this study is guided by the theory of planned behaviour (TPB). The TPB was proposed by Ajzen (1985) and posits that intentions are determinant of behavior which in turns depends on person's attitude, his subjective norms and the perceived behavioural control..

Statement of the Research Problem

Having established that students' positive attitude towards chemistry is congruent to their achievement (Al-Mutawah & Fateel, 2018; Montes et al., 2018), teachers and stakeholders in education are compelled to understand and revamp students' attitude in order to support their achievement in chemistry. This is because, even though several instructional strategies were introduced to enhance achievement in chemistry, students' performance in Colleges of Education is still worrisome. This claim is evident in the haphazard trend in performance of students in chemistry in the Department of Chemistry, Federal Colleges of Education, Zaria 2020-2023 as shown in table 1 below, where many of the total enrolments in the years under review are failing and even those that are passing, most of them passed with low grades usually Ds and Es (Examination office, Department of Chemistry, F.C.E, Zaria, 2024), this could be the consequences of negligence of their attitude towards the subject. Attitude towards learning plays a central role in achievement in science. Positive attitude are considered to be the basis for optimism which in in turn enhance achievement through persistence and resilience (Mokoro et al., 2014).

Table 1: NCE Students Chemistry performance from 2019 to 2020

Academic Year	2020	2021	2022
NCE I			
Total (%)	384(100)	338(100)	472(100)
Pass (%)	247(64.32)	200(59.17)	282(59.70)
Fail (%)	137(35.68)	138(40.83)	190(40.30)
NCE II			
Total (%)	325(100)	331(100)	448(100)
Pass (%)	164(50.46)	165(49.85)	221(49.33)
Fail (%)	161(49.54)	166(50.15)	227(50.67)
NCE III			
Total (%)	336(100)	268(100)	375(100)
Pass (%)	171(50.89)	154(57.46)	208(55.47)
Fail (%)	165(49.91)	114(42.54)	167(44.53)

Source: Examination office, Department of Chemistry, F.C.E, Zaria, 2024

On the other hand, negative attitude could breed anxiety and consequently, worsen students' achievement in sciences. Hence, the factors influencing students' attitude towards chemistry should not be disregarded, Factors, such as teachers' characteristics, parental influence, grade level, gender, motivation, depression, anxiety, instructional methods, interest, classroom environment, perceived difficulty, relevance of curriculum and so on were considered to influence students' attitude towards chemistry. However, attitude, instructional methods, gender and grade level were prominent among these factors (Musengimana et al., 2021).

Objectives of the study

The objectives through which the aim could be achieved are to;

1. Assess the level of attitude exhibited on acquiring chemistry content knowledge among students in Federal College of Education, Zaria.
2. Find out the difference between level of attitude exhibited on acquiring chemistry content knowledge between male

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and female students in Federal College of Education, Zaria.

3. Find out the difference between level of attitude exhibited on acquiring chemistry content knowledge between levels one, two and in Federal College of Education, Zaria.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of attitude exhibited on acquiring chemistry content knowledge among students in Federal College of Education, Zaria?
2. Is there significant difference on the level of attitude exhibited on acquiring chemistry content knowledge between male and female students in Federal College of Education, Zaria?
3. Is there significant difference on the level of attitude exhibited on acquiring chemistry content knowledge between levels one, two and in Federal College of Education, Zaria?

Methodology

Descriptive survey design was adopted in this study. The population of the study consists of all chemistry students in Federal College of Education Zaria, during the 2023/2024 academic session, sample size of the study consist of 150 (50 Male and 100 Female) chemistry students across all levels. The sample size was arrived at using simple random sampling technique.

A questionnaire was used to collect the data and was adapted from the Attitude towards Chemistry Index (ATCI) by Martha Tapia (Tapia, 1996; Tapia & Marsh, 2000b; Tapia & Marsh, 2004). The adapted ATCI consisted of forty questions and was answered based on a four-point Likert scale. The ATCI consisted of four Domains: The Motivation, Enjoyment, Value and self-confidence. There are five questions corresponding to the motivation domain, ten questions measuring Enjoyment and Value each and fifteen questions for Self-confidence domain.

The instrument was subjected to expert suggestions and comments which were incorporated before administering. Forty Nigeria Certificate in Education Chemistry students from FCE Kano participated in the pilot study. Reliability coefficient of 0.88 was obtained using Cronbach's alpha reliability test which shows the instrument to be reliable.

The participants' overall attitude was determined based on the total score of the ATCI. Possible scores range from a minimum of 40 to a maximum of 160 since a 4-point Likert scale was used. For analysis the ranges of scores were divided into 3 portions. Scores ranging from 40-80 indicated a poor attitude, 81-119 a moderate attitude and 120-160 a good attitude.

For research questions 1, means, percentages and standard deviation were used in the analysis and for research questions 2 and 3, independent samples T-test and One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) were explored at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the level of attitude exhibited on acquiring chemistry content knowledge among students in Federal College of Education, Zaria?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of general attitude

	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev.
General Attitude	150	60	160	117.2	23.4

As seen in Table 1, the attitude of the Nigeria Certificate in Education students on acquisition of Chemistry content knowledge was moderate (mean = 117.2). In particular, the majority of the population (63.7%) had moderate attitudes.

Table 2: Distribution of General attitude among participants

Score Range	Description	Frequency	%
40-80	Poor	25	10.1
81-119	Moderate	85	63.7
120-160	Good	40	26.2

When one considers the large range in score, 60-160 (Table 2) it is recognized that the attitude of the Nigeria Certificate in Education students on acquisition of Chemistry content knowledge widely varies.

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Research Question 2: Is there significant difference on the level of attitude exhibited on acquiring chemistry content knowledge between male and female students in Federal College of Education, Zaria?

Table 3: Difference in General attitude based on gender

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Df	T	Sig.
Male	50	106.2	20.2	123	-0.476	0.635
Female	100	118.7	24.2			

Table 3 shows the difference in means and standard deviation as well as results from the T-test when considering the difference between the attitudes of male and female Chemistry. The females have better attitudes than males on acquisition of Chemistry content knowledge however, this difference was not significant ($t = -0.476$, $p = 0.635$).

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Research Question 3: Is there significant difference on the level of attitude exhibited on acquiring chemistry content knowledge between levels one, two and in Federal College of Education, Zaria?

Table 4: Difference in general attitude towards Chemistry based on level of study

Levels	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	Df	F	Sig
NCE I	50	109.2	24.7	60	160			
NCE II	50	110.8	23.5	83	144	3,234	1.789	0.182
NCE III	50	112.7	21.3	80	154			

In terms of level of study (Table 4), there is a slight decrease in the general attitude of the participants as the level of study increased although this change was not statistically significant ($F[3,120] = 1.789, P = 0.182$).

Discussion of Findings

Result from table 1 shows that Nigeria Certificate in Education Chemistry students have a combination of both positive and negative attitudes on acquisition of chemistry content knowledge. Table 2 further suggests that only 10.1% of the population had poor attitudes and 26.2% had good attitudes towards Chemistry. Moreover, the fact that only 26.2% of the population had an overall good attitude suggests that over 70% of the chemistry students do not have good attitudes towards Chemistry. This may explain why to lecturers it appears as if Nigeria Certificate in Education Chemistry students lack some background in Chemistry. Table 3 shows that the females have better attitudes than males on acquisition of Chemistry content knowledge, however, this difference was not significant ($t = -0.476, p = 0.635$). This is not surprising since as opined by Ogunkola & Garner-O'Neale (2013) in the Caribbean there are no marked differences between males and females in various sciences including Chemistry in the area of achievement which can be linked to attitude although the relationship is complicated. This is in line with the work of (Frost et al., 1994; Orhun, 2007; Osborne et. al., 2003; Townsend & Wilton, 2003)

In terms of level of study (Table 4), there is a slight decrease in the general attitude of the participants as the level of study increased although this change was not statistically significant ($F [3,120] = 1.789, P = 0.182$). This finding agree with that of Leah Garner-O'Neale (2015), McLeod (1994) and Ozgun-Koca (2010) who suggest that as students' progress in school their attitudes towards Chemistry decline. It is expected that students will develop a better understanding of how Chemistry concepts are used overtime as they progress. When students are introduced to new theories they do not immediately have a complete understanding of the concepts, as students advance to higher levels, the previous Chemistry concepts and skills which were taught are reinforced thus helping to provide them with a better understanding; which should create a better attitude towards Chemistry as they progress through the levels. However, Ali & Reid (2012) also reported that as students grow older and more forward their attitudes tend to worsen due to increase in workload.

Conclusion

Among the Nigeria Certificate in Education Chemistry students at Federal College of Education, Zaria, the overall attitude towards Chemistry depicted was moderate in the ATCI used. There was no statistical significant differences between gender or across grade levels as it relates to the overall attitude of the Nigeria Certificate in Education Chemistry students at Federal College of Education, Zaria, a decline in positive attitudes of students towards Chemistry was revealed as their level of study increases, and this was attributed to high demand that learning required at the higher levels and the low efforts that students make particularly due to the lack of motivation.

Recommendations

1. Chemistry lecturers can play a significant role in bridging the gap in Chemistry between low input of the students and high demand from the workload by making Chemistry vivid and easy to understand, in order to stimulate student's intellectual curiosity which in turn leads to learning enhancement regardless of their career choice, this can also help to build self-confidence.
2. Chemistry lecturers can extrinsically motivate students by application of friendly presentations, utilization of analogies and co-relation with everyday life. This can help to bridge the gap between low input of the student and high demand of the workload.
3. Federal government should provide facilities such as laboratory apparatus and equipment, computers etc. necessary for the teaching and learning chemistry at NCE level, which if effectively utilized could contribute positively in influencing the attitude of students on acquisition of chemistry content knowledge.

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